

Manual Tracking Control with Amplitude and Rate Constrained Actuators

R.B. Miller (rbmiller@afit.af.mil) and M. Pachter (mpachter@afit.af.mil)
Air Force Institute of Technology, Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433

Abstract

Tracking control in a receding horizon framework is considered and a novel, optimization-based, linear tracking control strategy - Linear Quadratic Tracking (LQT) is devised. LQT yields a closed-form solution to optimization-based tracking of a dynamic reference signal $r(t)$, in the face of both rate and amplitude actuator constraints; Actuator dynamics are included. Also, there is no inherent requirement for stability of the open-loop plant. At the same time, full state feedback is assumed. The detrimental effects of the actuator constraints are mitigated by giving the control system a nonlinearly modified, feasible reference signal $r'(t)$, as required to prevent downstream actuator saturations from occurring. Thus, the controller generated signal never infringes on the saturation bounds, and windup is precluded. The analytic solution to the linear, unconstrained, tracking problem meets the small signal performance specs and is stable. The proposed piecewise linear closed form solution to the constrained tracking problem yields good responses to large inputs and at the same time requires modest on-line computation, and hence is implementable in real-time.

1. Introduction

Actuator saturation is a topic of active research in control theory, [1]-[7]. Most of the current literature is geared toward the regulation and set-point control problems as opposed to tracking control, and thus does not directly apply to maneuvering and manual flight control. Also, most of the work fails to address actuator rate saturation. Notable exceptions concerning tracking control are [3], [4], [6], [7], and rate saturation is explicitly addressed in [6], [7]. Additionally, in the tradition of Popov's work [8], most papers are restricted to stable open-loop plants. Unstable plants are specifically addressed in [3], [5], [7]. Additionally, by neglecting actuator dynamics altogether, actuator constraints are most often treated as control constraints, whereas, particularly in "high gain" flight control, actuator dynamics should be included, in which case state constraints are introduced.

When an exogenous reference signal is being considered in the literature, the concept of tracking a less aggressive reference as a means of avoiding saturation has been proposed - see, e.g., [3], [4], [7]. Thus, the *reference governor* concept is advanced in [3]. The original continuous time developments are rigorous, but computationally complex. In the present paper, a novel, closed form optimization-based approach which is grounded in tracking control and thus allows for the tracking of a less aggressive pilot input reference signal as a means of avoiding saturation

is proposed. The actuator saturation problem (both amplitude and rate) is addressed from a manual flight control perspective. Hence, tracking control is considered. Actuator dynamics are included. Also, there is no requirement for stability of the open-loop plant. At the same time, full state feedback is assumed. An optimization-based, nonlinear, but *closed-form* feedback control strategy for the actuator constrained tracking problem is proposed. The exogenous system input is the reference signal from the pilot. The approach acknowledges the existence of hard constraints from the outset, and "small signal" performance is not sacrificed.

2. Manual Flight Control

Manual flight control entails a pilot flying an aircraft "by the seat of his pants" in order to satisfy a mission objective, e.g., in military aviation one objective is to engage enemy aircraft. Thus, manual flight control calls for tracking control. The tracking task begins at some point subsequent to take-off and cruise (where the aircraft could be flown by the autopilot). Thus, the manual tracking task is an "open-ended" problem which evolves in time; its duration is unknown prior to the completion of the task. Moreover, in the case of aircraft manual flight control, the tracking situation arises where the reference signal is not known in advance. Furthermore, these control problems are strictly of a dynamic and transient nature. "Steady state" is meaningless in maneuvering and manual flight control. All of this stands in stark contrast to the classical regulation paradigm. These considerations, and bearing in mind the very nature of hard actuator constraints, indicate that the manual flight control problem should be addressed in the time domain. Furthermore, the constrained actuator control problem is most commonly treated as a control constrained problem, when in fact, it is a state/control constrained problem.

The block diagram of Figure 1 represents the tracking feedback control problem at hand. The physical aircraft includes control surfaces which are positioned by dynamic actuators. An appropriate aircraft model requires an augmentation of the airframe dynamics with the actuator dynamics. The controller's output is $u \equiv \delta_c$, which, when linear controllers are employed, is unconstrained. The control surface deflection δ which is the plant's input, is however, constrained due to physical limitations of the mechanical actuator. The basic airframe dynamics (plant) are described by

$$\mathbf{x}_{p,k+1} = \mathbf{A}_p \mathbf{x}_{p,k} + \mathbf{b}_p \delta_k + \zeta d \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{p,k}$ is the plant state vector at time k , \mathbf{A}_p and \mathbf{b}_p are the dynamics matrix and input vector respectively, δ_k is the

control surface deflection at time k , ζ is a disturbance input vector, d is a known and constant disturbance, and the output of interest is $y_{k+1} = \mathbf{c}_p \mathbf{x}_{p,k+1}$. The known constant disturbance d is included in anticipation of the need to linearize the plant about a non-trim point. \mathbf{A}_p is not necessarily Hurwitz. Furthermore, the control surface displacement is constrained in both amplitude and rate, viz.,

$$\delta_{\min} \leq \delta_{k+1} \leq \delta_{\max} \text{ and } \Delta\delta_{\min} \leq (\delta_{k+1} - \delta_k) \leq \Delta\delta_{\max} \quad (2)$$

The control system supplies actuator commands (the control signal, $u_k \equiv \delta_{c_k}$), resulting in control surface deflections according to the actuator dynamics, viz., $\mathbf{x}_{\delta,k+1} = \mathbf{A}_\delta \mathbf{x}_{\delta,k} + \mathbf{b}_\delta \delta_{c_k}$ and $\delta_{k+1} = \mathbf{c}_\delta \mathbf{x}_{\delta,k+1}$. $\mathbf{x}_{\delta,k}$ is the internal state of the actuator at time k . Thus, the flight control system under consideration entails an augmentation of the airframe dynamics. An integrator state z for the purpose of implementing integral action in the time domain is also included and adds a pole at the (s -plane) origin. The latter may be necessary in order to meet tracking performance specifications. Hence, the augmented control system ensues $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{b} u_k + \Gamma_1 r_{k+1} + \Gamma_2 d$, $y_{k+1} = \mathbf{c} \mathbf{x}_{k+1}$, where

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{p,k} \\ \mathbf{x}_{\delta,k} \\ z_{k+1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_p & \mathbf{b}_p \mathbf{c}_\delta & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{A}_\delta & \mathbf{0} \\ -T \mathbf{c}_p \mathbf{A}_p & \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$\mathbf{b} = [\mathbf{0} \mid \mathbf{b}_\delta \mid \mathbf{0}]^T$, $\Gamma_1 = [\mathbf{0} \mid \mathbf{0} \mid T]^T$, $\Gamma_2 = [\zeta \mid \mathbf{0} \mid \mathbf{0}]^T$, and $\mathbf{c} = [\mathbf{c}_p \mid \mathbf{0} \mid \mathbf{0}]$, and where the respective augmented state, input vector, output vector and disturbance input vector are \mathbf{x}_k , \mathbf{b} , \mathbf{c}^T , $\Gamma_2 \in \mathbf{R}^n$, the augmented dynamics matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times n}$, the control signal, the output and the (constant and known) disturbance are u_k , y_{k+1} , d , $\in \mathbf{R}^1$, respectively, the "time" variable is k , and the initial state $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbf{R}^n$ is known. Note that in the augmented system the additional input vector Γ_1 is included to accommodate the use of integral action, and T is the sampling interval. The above system description readily reveals that a constrained state problem is in fact at hand.

3. Tracking Control

In [7] it has been recognized that a Receding Horizon Predictive Control (RHPC) approach is well suited to the tracking control problem and thus applicable to manual flight control. In [7] the LQ and Linear Programming (LP) optimization paradigms have been combined to yield a hybrid approach to the control-constrained tracking problem within the RHPC framework. The LQ/LP approach to tracking ensures that for some time into the future only *feasible* signals are generated by the controller, which do not exceed the prescribed control constraints. The present paper builds on the previous work, to yield a one-step ahead constraint enforcement scheme which is readily implementable in closed form. The need for complex on-line numerical optimization is eliminated and real-time operation is facilitated. Additionally, in this paper the actuator amplitude constraints are properly incorporated as state

constraints, and the actuator rate constraints are properly incorporated as control and state constraints. Also, special attention is given to the reference signal extrapolation and the selection of the planning horizon N .

The tracking task requires the system output to follow an exogenous reference, i.e., it is required that $y_{k+1} \approx r_{k+1}$. In a RHPC formulation, the control task is addressed from each time step k over a finite planning horizon N . An LQ approach is employed, and the quadratic performance functional

$$J = \sum_{m=k}^{k+N-1} [Q_p (y_{m+1} - r_{m+1})^2 + Q_l z_{m+1}^2 + R u_m^2] \quad (4)$$

is to be minimized at each time step k , where the scalar weights $Q_p \geq 0$, $Q_l \geq 0$ and $R \geq 0$.

Now, as discussed previously, in the manual tracking problem it is required to continually follow an unknown, exogenous reference as it becomes available in time. Thus, r_{k+1} is not known until time k , at which time r_{k+2}, \dots, r_{k+N} are not known. Hence, at time k it is impossible to explicitly evaluate (or much less, minimize) the performance functional J given in Eq (4) for a given tracking task until it is over; clearly, at this point it is too late to utilize this information in the control of the vehicle during the tracking task. Thus, in order to employ the optimal control method, the reference signal r_k must be prespecified over the planning horizon. Since this is not feasible in the case of manual, viz., real-time (causal) tracking control, the reference must be predicted into the future based on the currently available reference signal r_{k+1} and the past history of the reference signal. In the present paper, polynomial extrapolation is used. It would be ill-advised to make long term predictions, so a receding horizon approach is used to break up the infinite horizon tracking problem into an open-ended sequence of finite horizon optimization problems based on short-term only predictions of the reference.

At each time instant k , i.e., within each RHPC window, the reference signal is extrapolated over the planning horizon N . The predicted reference signal is denoted by \hat{r}_{k+n} , $n = 2, \dots, N$. Thus, over the duration of the optimization window, the reference signal is $(r_{k+1}, \hat{r}_{k+2}, \dots, \hat{r}_{k+N})^T$. At each time step k , the (unconstrained) optimal control sequence $\mathbf{u}^* = (u^*_0, u^*_1, \dots, u^*_{N-1})^T$ for tracking the extrapolated reference sequence $\hat{\mathbf{r}} = (r_1, \hat{r}_2, \dots, \hat{r}_N)^T$ is determined, such that the quadratic performance functional

$$J = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} [Q_p (y_{n+1} - \hat{r}_{n+1})^2 + Q_l z_{n+1}^2 + R u_n^2] \quad (5)$$

is minimized. In the sequel, the subscript k will be used to represent real-time instants, while, within a given receding horizon window, the subscript n will be used. Thus, each u_k and r_{k+1} over the tracking task will be represented by a u_0 and r_1 respectively in one of the receding horizon windows.

According to the receding horizon modus operandi, u_0 represents an actual system input. The remaining control

signals u_1, \dots, u_{N-1} do not represent physically realized inputs to the system (and do not require explicit evaluation). Furthermore, at any given time instant k in the *system time reference*, x_0 from the *window time reference* represents x_k , thus state feedback action is achieved via the receding horizon formulation.

4. Reference Signal Prediction

In each Receding Horizon (RH) window an extrapolation of the reference signal is performed. A two-stage extrapolation scheme is investigated, where each stage is based on a polynomial extrapolation of the reference signal of the form $r_n = a_0 + a_1 n + a_2 n^2 + \dots + a_p n^p$, $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$. In the first stage a p -th order polynomial extrapolation of the pilot supplied reference signal is performed. The present and p past values of the pilot supplied reference are used to predict what is actually desired of the system over the planning horizon. This is necessary in order to determine the right (future) anchor point for the second stage interpolation. The first stage extrapolation involves the solution of a set of $p+1$ linear equations. The second stage then involves the determination of the *feasible* reference sequence, r' which can be tracked without violating the control constraints. Stage two is similar to stage one, except that it is desired to express this sequence in terms of the known, previously applied values of the reference signal, the above mentioned right anchor point and an adjustable reference signal at time $n = 1$, r'_1 . This second interpolation is accomplished using a p' -th order polynomial fit. To completely determine the polynomial coefficients, $p'+1$ boundary conditions are required. However, since the proposed control strategy requires expressing the extrapolated reference sequence in terms of r'_1 , only p' additional conditions must be explicitly known. These boundary conditions consist of $p'-1$ previously applied values of the reference signal, and \hat{r}_N , the right anchor point. The two-stage reference extrapolation concept is illustrated in Figure 2, where a three points based second-order ($p=p'=2$), parabolic, extrapolation is used in both stages. The extrapolation is performed at time k . At the conclusion of the second stage extrapolation, r' is linear in r'_1 , and thus, the feasible reference sequence can be written in the form

$$r' = [r'_1 \quad r'_2 \quad \dots \quad r'_N]^T = k r'_1 + h \quad (6)$$

where $k = [1 \quad k_2 \quad \dots \quad k_N]^T$, $h = [0 \quad h_2 \quad \dots \quad h_N]^T$, and where the k_n are constants determined by the order p of the polynomial extrapolation, and the h_n depend only on the present and p past values of the pilot commanded reference signal and the p' previously determined feasible reference values corresponding to the p' previous pilot commanded reference values. In addition, the coefficients h_n are linear in these past and present reference values. Thus, h is also constant within a given window. Hence, during the current window, and as it relates to the required optimiza-

tion, r' is explicitly known as a linear function of the as of yet to be obtained r'_1 .

5. Unconstrained Optimal Control

Given the discrete time system of Eq (3), and with the reference signal r_k stipulated for all $1 \leq k \leq N$, the unconstrained LQT problem with *finite* planning horizon N can be posed as a linear quadratic optimization problem in the control sequence $u = (u_0, u_1, \dots, u_{N-1})^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$ by considering the vectors $\hat{r} = (r_1, \hat{r}_2, \dots, \hat{r}_N)^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$, $y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N)^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$, and $z = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N)^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$, where u represents an N -point input sequence, \hat{r} is the extrapolated reference sequence, y is the corresponding N -point output sequence, and z is the N -point integrator "charge." Using this vector notation, the convex cost functional Eq (5) can be written $J = Q_p [y - \hat{r}]^T [y - \hat{r}] + Q_I z^T z + R u^T u$. The optimal control sequence u^* for the unconstrained problem over the planning horizon N is given by $u = u^*$ such that $\partial J / \partial u = 0$. The "inputs" to the optimization in each window are the current state x_k (referred to as x_0 within the window) and the prespecified (extrapolated) reference signal \hat{r} , currently referred to as r , which are used to determine the unconstrained optimal control sequence $u^*(r; x_0)$. In each window, r is parametrized by r_1 .

Direct substitution of the explicit solution of the open-loop difference equation into the quadratic functional (5) and solving $\partial J / \partial u = 0$ yields the closed form optimal control sequence $u^*(r; x_0) = \Lambda r + \Pi x_0 + O d$, where the coefficient matrices $\Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $\Pi \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times n}$ and $O \in \mathbb{R}^N$ depend only on the system parameters (A , b , c , Γ_1 , Γ_2) and the LQ weights Q_p , Q_I and R . An important observation is that u^* is linear in both r and the initial state $x_0 \equiv x_k$. Hence, the unconstrained LQT optimal control solution is specified linearly in terms of the known plant parameters in the coefficient matrices Λ , Π and O , known past values and the present value of the reference sequence in h and r_1 , the current plant state x_0 , and the known and constant disturbance d .

6. Control Constraints

The optimal control sequence as determined in the above may violate the actuator constraints. In order to avoid the detrimental effects of hard saturation it may become necessary to modify the exogenous command input to the system and determine a *feasible* reference sequence r' which can be tracked in a given window within the bounds of the actuator constraints. Since the actual system control $u_k = u_0$ is the only element of u which will actually be applied to the system, only saturations at time $k + 1$ directly attributable to $u_k = u_0$ will be accounted for. Now, $u_k^* = u_k^*(r; x_k)$, and thus, the question arises: If the input u_k will induce either a rate or amplitude saturation, what is the *best* reference r' which can be optimally tracked such that the control $u'_k = u_k^*(r'; x_k)$ will not induce an actuator saturation at time $k + 1$? "Best" here refers to closeness to

the pilot input reference signal. Since the extrapolation is done such that the reference $\mathbf{r}' = \mathbf{k}r_1 + \mathbf{h}$, where the \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{h} vectors are effectively constants within each RH window, the above question is tantamount to determining a feasible r_1' . Thus, $u_0 \equiv u_k$ can be written in the form

$$u_k = \mathbf{k}_x \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{k}_r [r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}]^T + \mathbf{k}_{r^*} [r_{k+2-p}^*, \dots, r_k^*]^T + k_r r_{k+1}' + k_d d \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{k}_x = \Pi(1,:)$ (the first row of Π), $k_r = [\Lambda \mathbf{k}](1)$ (the first element of the vector $\Lambda \mathbf{k}$), $k_d = \mathbf{O}(1)$, and k_r, k_{r^*} result from algebraic manipulations on $\Lambda \mathbf{h}$. For example, in the case $p=p'=2$,

$$\mathbf{k}_r = \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^N (m^2 - m) \Lambda(1, m) \right) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{N} \right) & \frac{N+1}{N-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$k_{r^*} = \sum_{m=1}^N \left[\left(1 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{N} \right) m + \frac{1}{N} m^2 \right) \Lambda(1, m) \right]$$

Now, $\delta_{k+1} = \mathbf{c}_\delta \mathbf{x}_{\delta_{k+1}} = \mathbf{c}_\delta (\mathbf{A}_\delta \mathbf{x}_{\delta_k} + \mathbf{b}_\delta \delta_{c_k})$, and $\delta_{c_k}^* \equiv u_k^* \equiv u_0^*$ from the preceding development. Thus, the actuator displacement constraints of Eq (2) applied at time k can be transformed into explicit constraints on r_1' given by

$$f_d \leq r_1' \leq g_d \quad (8)$$

where the numbers

$$f_d = \frac{\delta_{\min} - \mathbf{c}_a [\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{b} \mathbf{k}_x] \mathbf{x}_k}{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r} - \frac{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} \mathbf{k}_r [r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}]^T}{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r} - \frac{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} (\mathbf{k}_{r^*} [r_{k+2-p}^*, \dots, r_k^*]^T + k_d d)}{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r}$$

$$g_d = \frac{\delta_{\max} - \mathbf{c}_a [\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{b} \mathbf{k}_x] \mathbf{x}_k}{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r} - \frac{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} \mathbf{k}_r [r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}]^T}{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r} - \frac{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} (\mathbf{k}_{r^*} [r_{k+2-p}^*, \dots, r_k^*]^T + k_d d)}{\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r}$$

and $\mathbf{c}_a = [\mathbf{0} \mid \mathbf{c}_\delta \mid \mathbf{0}]$. In the event that $\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r < 0$, the inequality signs of Eq (8) are reversed.

The actuator rate constraints of Eq (2) are transformed into constraints on r_1' in a similar fashion, to obtain the constraints

$$f_r \leq r_1' \leq g_r \quad (9)$$

and the most strict inequalities are used to determine r_{\min} and r_{\max} such that Eqs (8) and (9) are both satisfied when $r_{\min} \leq r_1' \leq r_{\max}$. Here, $r_{\min} = \max(f_d, f_r)$ and $r_{\max} = \min(g_d, g_r)$ for $\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r > 0$, or $r_{\min} = \max(g_d, g_r)$ and $r_{\max} = \min(f_d, f_r)$ for $\mathbf{c}_a \mathbf{b} k_r < 0$. r_1' is chosen accordingly, viz., $r_1' = r_{\min}$, for $r_1 < r_{\min}$, $r_1' = r_1$, for $r_{\min} \leq r_1 \leq r_{\max}$, and $r_1' = r_{\max}$, for $r_1 > r_{\max}$.

This value of r_1' is inserted into Eq (7), thus obtaining the feasible control signal. Note: During small signal operation, $r_{k+1}' = r_{k+1}$, and the linear performance characteristics are preserved, thus small signal performance is not sacrificed to accommodate the actuator constraints.

Observe that $|r_{k+1}'| \leq |r_{k+1}|$ does not necessarily hold. The case $|r_{k+1}'| > |r_{k+1}|$ is indeed possible, and, e.g., it is also possible that $r_{k+1} = 0$ whereas $r_{k+1}' \neq 0$. Hence, a rather general adjustment of the exogenous reference signal is employed in order to address the manual tracking problem with both amplitude and rate control constraints.

7. Flight Control Example

The aircraft plant used here represents the short period dynamics of an F-16 derivative, at the flight condition 10000 ft, Mach 0.7. The bare plant's state space model is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\alpha} \\ \dot{q} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_\alpha & Z_q \\ M_\alpha & M_q \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ q \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} Z_\delta \\ M_\delta \end{bmatrix} \delta \quad (10)$$

where the units of angle of attack α and pitch rate q are rad and rad/second respectively, with $Z_\alpha = -1.15$, $Z_q = 0.9937$, $Z_\delta = -0.177$, $M_\alpha = 3.724$, $M_q = -1.26$, and $M_\delta = -19.5$. Additionally, a first order actuator with bandwidth of 20 rad/sec is used, with amplitude and rate constraints of 0.37 rad and 1 rad/sec, respectively. The augmented system including the actuator state and an integral control state, is discretized using a sampling interval of $T=0.01$ sec, and pitch rate, q , is the output of interest.

In terms of the reference signal prediction, $p=p'=2$ has fared well in simulation studies, without any appreciable gain in performance by using higher order extrapolations. The physical prediction horizon of the extrapolation is given by TN , which is in this case 0.01N sec. The tracking characteristics of the closed loop system depend on Q_i , Q_p , R , and N . Increasing Q_i , Q_p , or N , or decreasing R translates to a higher gain controller, and thus tighter tracking. Thus, in terms of the tracking performance, any desired characteristics can be obtained with a fixed N , by appropriately adjusting the LQ weights. Of course, higher gain controllers increase the likelihood of infringement of the actuator constraints, but the LQT controller mitigates these effects.

Parabolic extrapolation, viz., $p=p'=2$ is used and the explicit control law is thus given by

$$u_k = \delta_{c_k} = \mathbf{k}_x \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{k}_r [r_{k-1}, r_k, r_{k+1}]^T + k_{r^*} r_k^* + k_r r_{k+1}' \quad (11)$$

where the specific gain values depend only on the horizon N , the plant parameters \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{b} , \mathbf{c} , and the LQ weights Q_i , Q_p , and R . r_k^* is the feasible reference which was determined at the previous time step. The disturbance $d = 0$. The input signal used for each simulation is a pitch doublet pre-filtered by the flying qualities/reference model's dynamics $(19.5s + 23)/(s^2 + 7s + 16.25)$.

The proposed LQT tracker is compared to a straightforward infinite horizon LQR based tracker, a simplification where a plant input signal of $u_k = r_{k+1} - \mathbf{k}_{LQR} \mathbf{x}_k$ is used, and where \mathbf{k}_{LQR} is the infinite horizon LQR control law gain. This simple regulator-based tracking control law is conceptually flawed, since $\mathbf{k} \mathbf{x} \neq y$ and the command u_k is formed by mixing "apples and oranges," but is nevertheless commonly used, see e.g., [2]. Furthermore, regulator-based trackers of this type may require special consideration

in the selection of the LQ weights to ensure that a steady state gain of 1 is achieved. Hence, the inclusion of the integral control state in the present paper, ensures that the regulator-based tracker will have unity dc gain. In general, however, integral control is not required for tracking when state feedback is used and the LQT paradigm is employed; rather, it is needed to address model uncertainty and unmodeled disturbance rejection.

The simulation results in Fig. 3 demonstrate that the proposed optimization-based, RHPC formulation and the use of the extrapolated reference signal does improve the tracking performance. In this example, the weights $Q_1 = 47.0$, $Q_p = 0.29$, and $R = 0.91$ are chosen. Now, as N becomes large, the state feedback gain vector approaches the (infinite-horizon) LQR solution provided gain. For the example at hand, it transpires, that for $N=60$, there is no appreciable difference between k_x and the infinite horizon LQR gain k_{LQR} , and thus there is nothing to be gained by selecting $N>60$ (Note that this value depends not only on the plant parameters, but also on the LQ weights). Thus, for a fair comparison, the LQT optimization and prediction horizon is selected $N=60$ (physically, the reference signal is predicted 0.6 sec into the future), and the actuator constraints are not enforced. The benefits of the LQT approach, viz. tighter tracking, are evident from Fig 3. An examination of the closed-loop frequency responses resulting from these two control strategies shows that the beneficial effect of including the reference signal in the optimization is to increase the bandwidth and minimize the phase lag of the closed-loop system.

The next simulation demonstrates the detrimental effects of actuator saturations when they are not accounted for in the design process. Again, the regulator-based tracker of the previous example is considered, and the results are compared to the performance of the LQT controller. In this case, the planning horizon $N=5$ is used in the LQT controller, and to greatly exacerbate the actuator saturation problem, a very high gain controller is considered, and it is attempted to track a high amplitude reference signal. Specifically to obtain high gain action, the LQ weights are modified from the previous example: Q_p is increased by a factor of 32, and Q_1 is increased by a factor of 60. Furthermore, the amplitude of the reference signal is tripled.

First, the unconstrained response is shown in Fig. 4, where it is noted that the LQT controller achieves tighter tracking. The constrained response is shown in Figs. 5 and 6. As expected, the LQT response is somewhat degraded - the constrained system simply cannot perfectly track this reference signal. The response, nevertheless is relatively well behaved. Furthermore, it should be noted that the apparent hard saturations in rate are in fact imposed by the controller. Thus the feasible references include those which result in the actuator riding the limit, but not those which would exceed those constraints. The heuristic LQR-based tracker (which did not account for the actuator constraints in the design process) on the other hand, yields totally un-

acceptable performance. Thus the proposed LQT strategy can deliver tight (high gain) dynamic tracking performance and mitigate the hard actuator constraints effects.

8. Discussion and Conclusions

The approach presented here yields a computationally inexpensive, closed-form and real-time implementable (causal) solution to the constrained tracking problem. The solution is given by an explicit control law of the form

$$u_k = k_x x_k + k_r [r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}]^T + k_{r^*} [r_{k+2-p}^*, \dots, r_k^*]^T + k_{r'} r'_{k+1} + k_d d \quad (12)$$

where the gains k_x , k_r , k_{r^*} , $k_{r'}$ and k_d are constants which depend only on the horizon N , the plant parameters A , b , c , Γ_1 , Γ_2 and the LQ weights Q_1 , Q_p , and R , and therefore can be computed off-line. x_k is the current state, r_j are the pilot's commands, r'_{k+1} is the current feasible reference, and the r_j^* are the previous feasible (and therefore, applied to the control system and known) reference signals, and d is the known constant disturbance. Thus, the constrained linear quadratic tracking (LQT) solution is expressed as a fixed gain controller which operates on the current values of the state, reference input, and feasible reference, p previous values of the pilot desired reference, and $p-1$ previous values of the (actually input) feasible reference. Note however that this control is only linear in appearance, for in the case of large inputs or strong deviations from trim the feasible reference signal r'_{k+1} is nonlinearly determined.

When actuator saturation is not exercised, as in small signal operation, the signals r^* and r' are simply the pilot input r , and full linear action is realized. Thus, when the actuator saturation limits are not infringed, the control u_k is linear in x_k , $r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}$, and d , and Eq (7) can be written $u_k = k_x x_k + k_R [r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}]^T + k_d d$, with $k_R = k_r + [0 \mid k_{r^*} \mid k_{r'}]$. The inclusion of the reference signal's past values introduces additional dynamics and causes an augmentation of the closed-loop system, yielding p additional states. In the linear case, however, the only effect on the closed-loop system lies in the number and placement of the closed-loop zeros, as the additional p poles will always be at $s = -\infty$. In the constrained case, the control law is nonlinear due to the nonlinear calculation of r' in Eq (7), viz.,

$$u_k = k_x x_k + k_r [r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}]^T + k_{r^*} [r_{k+2-p}^*, \dots, r_k^*]^T + k_d d + k_{r'} f(x_k, r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}, r_{k+2-p}^*, \dots, r_k^*, d) \quad (13)$$

However, the function f is piecewise linear in its above listed arguments. The dependence of the nonlinear component f on not only previous (closed-loop system) input values, but also on previous state values (via the $r_{k+2-p}^*, \dots, r_k^*$) augments the system, for $r_{k+1}^* = f_{r^*}(x_k, r_{k+1-p}, \dots, r_{k+1}, r_{k+2-p}^*, \dots, r_k^*, d)$, and will clearly affect the closed-loop poles.

The presently proposed optimization-based approach to tracking includes actuator dynamics and accounts for both rate and displacement actuator (not control) constraints, addresses the dynamic and transient nature of the

manual tracking problem, has no inherent requirement for stability of the open-loop plant, and employs full state feedback. Furthermore, the resulting piecewise linear control law is computationally inexpensive, does not require the use of on-line numerical search/optimization routines, is easily implementable in real-time, and small signal performance is maintained. At the same time, good tracking responses to large exogenous (pilot) commands are obtained.

References

1. Campo, P.J. and M. Morari, "Robust Control of Processes Subject to Saturation Nonlinearities," *Computers chem Engng*, Vol 14, No 4/5, pp 343-358, 1990.
2. D'Azzo J.J. and C.H. Houpis, *Linear Control System Analysis & Design*, McGraw-Hill Inc, New York, 1988.
3. Gilbert, E.G., et al, "Nonlinear Control of Discrete-time Linear Systems with State and Control Constraints: A Reference Governor with Global Convergence Properties," *Proceedings of the 33rd Conference on Decision and Control*, Dec 1994, pp. 144-149.
4. Hanus, R., M., et al, "Conditioning technique, a general antiwindup and bumpless transfer method," *Automatica*, vol 23, pp 729-739, 1987.
5. Hess, R.A. and S.A. Snell, "Flight control design with actuator saturation: SISO systems with unstable plants," *AIAA 95-0336, 33rd Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit*, Jan 1995.
6. Kerasouris, P. and M. Athans, "Control systems with rate and magnitude saturation for neutrally stable open-loop systems," *Proceedings of the 29th Conference on Decision and Control*, pp 3404-9, vol 6, 1990.
7. Pachter, M., et al, "Control Reconfiguration with actuator rate saturation," *Proceedings of the American Control Conference*, pp 3495-3499, Seattle WA, June 1995.
8. Popov, V.M., *Hyperstability of Control Systems*, Springer, 1974.

Figure 1. Tracking Problem Block Diagram

Figure 2. Second Order 2-Stage Extrapolation

Figure 3. LQT (N=60) vs LQR (Unconstrained)

Figure 4. High Gain Tracking (Unconstrained)

Figure 5. High Gain Tracking (Constrained)

Figure 6. Control Surface Response